

**Modarese Bartar Quarterly
(MBQ)**
International Journal of Teachers and Students

Alzheimer's disease

2024, 1(3), 1-4

Elina Asadi

Farzanegan Elite Students' High school

Abstract

Considering the yearly rise in Alzheimer's disease, acknowledging this condition is a crucial step towards preventing it. This article discusses the causes, symptoms, ways of prevention and measures after the diagnosis of the disease. It also introduces new treatment methods.

This review presents a foundation for future researchers.

Keywords: warning signs, family support, medication treatment.

Introduction

The most prevalent form of memory loss is Alzheimer's disease. The issue begins with a brief memory lapse and could possibly end with the incapability to engage in a conversation and respond to the surroundings. The brain regions responsible for thinking, recall, and communication are affected by Alzheimer's disease.

A person's daily routine is seriously impacted by it.

Alzheimer's disease is a growing global problem that affects 50 million people worldwide. Experts predict that by 2050, this number will increase to over 155 million. More locally, in Iran, more than 700,000 people are currently battling this illness, making it a pressing wellness concern. The hidden magnitude of Alzheimer's disease in Iran makes the situation even more concerning. Dementia, including

Alzheimer's, is less common among individuals aged 65 to 69, with only three percent affected.

However, as people age, the risk dramatically increases. Surprisingly, the prevalence reaches 30 percent between the ages of 85 to 89.

There is an urgent need for greater awareness, research, and support to tackle this health crisis.

Information available about Alzheimer's

Scientists are still unsure about the underlying cause of Alzheimer's. It is hard to pinpoint a single cause, but there are several variables that could affect everyone differently.

The advancing age is the most well-known risk factor for the degenerative brain disorder. The development of Alzheimer's maybe linked to genetics, according to researchers. But genes are not always the same as destiny. In addition to these, diabetes, overweight, smoking, head injuries, depression, high blood presser, high cholesterol, and cardiovascular affects the progression of the disease.

Reducing the risk of Alzheimer's

If you live a healthy life, you can lower your chances of getting Alzheimer's disease. Two extensive, ongoing studies suggest that regular exercise, a balanced diet, moderate alcohol intake, avoiding tobacco use and good sleep quality may be beneficial.

The brain's changes can start long before you notice anything. Researchers are examining whether the effects of childhood education, nutrition, and environmental factors contribute to the onset of Alzheimer's disease.

the evidence from research shows that maintaining a healthy lifestyle, which has been shown to safeguard against diseases such as cancer, diabetes, and cardiovascular disease, may also mitigate the threat of subjective cognitive decline. There are eight ways to do that.

1. *Memory problems that make daily life difficult:*

It is common for individuals to overlook important events, repeat themselves, or rely on additional aids to aid in their memory, such as sticky notes or reminders.

2. *Struggles with routine chores:*

Having trouble doing daily tasks like cooking, driving, using a phone, or going to the store.

3. *Experiencing confusion regarding the time or location:*

Having difficulty comprehending an event that occurred later or recollecting its exact location.

4. *Issues with visual perception:*

Having greater difficulty in maintaining balance or assessing distance, and prone to spilling or dropping objects more frequently.

5. *Language difficulties:*

It is possible that you may encounter difficulties following or participating in a conversation, or in locating the appropriate term such as referring to the device on your wrist that displays the time instead of a watch.

6. *Judgment under siege:*

Being the victim of a scam, neglecting financial management, neglecting personal hygiene, or encountering difficulties in caring for a pet.

7. *Refraining from social interaction:*

Refraining from attending church or engaging in other activities as usual, and being unable to follow football matches or keep up with current events.

8. *Changes in how you feel and act:*

Being easily upset in everyday situations or being afraid or suspicious.

What to do when you get a diagnosis

Your doctor can check if your symptoms are related to Alzheimer's disease or something that can be fixed, like a vitamin shortage or medication side effects.

One can contemplate financial planning, develop advance directives, enroll in clinical trials, and anticipate healthcare requirements through an early diagnosis for oneself and their family.

Support for friends and family

Currently, numerous individuals with Alzheimer's disease are taken care of by their relatives at home. The act of providing care can be beneficial both for the caregiver and the individual being cared for. The caregiver may feel personal fulfillment from helping a family member or friend.

Improved family relations and new skills may be developed by it.

Sometimes it can be overwhelming to care for a person with Alzheimer's disease at home. Every day presents new challenges for the caretaker, who must contend with varying abilities and altering patterns of behavior. People with Alzheimer's need more attention as the disease progresses.

New medication treatment

"Donanemab" is a drug that can help people with early-stage Alzheimer's disease remember and think better.

It is used intravenously and may have side effects such as: headache, swelling and bleeding in the brain

Conclusion:

Giving importance to a healthy lifestyle and checking mental and physical health, as well as receiving family support, is incredibly effective in preventing Alzheimer's disease or reversing the disease progression.

Research further:

In the upcoming studies, drug treatment and how to reduce its side effects can be discussed.

References:

1. Matthews, K. A., Xu, W., Gaglioti, A. H., Holt, J. B., Croft, J. B., Mack, D., & McGuire, L. C. (2018). Racial and ethnic estimates of Alzheimer's disease and related dementias in the United States (2015–2060) in adults aged ≥ 65 years. *Alzheimer's & Dementia*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jalz.2018.06.3063>
2. Xu J, Kochanek KD, Sherry L, Murphy BS, Tejada-Vera B. Deaths: final data for 2007. National vital statistics reports; vol. 58, no. 19. Hyattsville, MD: National Center for Health Statistics. 2010.
3. Heron M. Deaths: leading causes for 2010. National vital statistics reports; vol. 62, no 6. Hyattsville, MD: National Center for Health Statistics. 2013.
4. Hurd MD, Martorell P, Delavande A, Mullen KJ, Langa KM. Monetary costs of dementia in the United States. *NEJM*. 2013;368(14):1326-34.
5. Tejada-Vera B. Mortality from Alzheimer's disease in the United States: data for 2000 and 2010. NCHS data brief, no 116. Hyattsville, MD: National Center for Health Statistics. 2013.
6. James BD, Leurgans SE, Hebert LE, et al. Contribution of Alzheimer disease to mortality in the United States. *Neurology*. 2014;82:1-6.
7. Retrieved from: <https://www.cdc.gov/aging/aginginfo>
8. <https://www.alzheimers.org.uk>